

A review of taxonomic structure of *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) scrobicolle* Kraatz, 1873 (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) from Turkey

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Abstract

Dorcadion scrobicolle Kraatz, 1873 is accepted with 8 subspecies. All subspecies are described. Three subspecies are described as new: *D. s. hroni* **ssp. n.** (Tokat province, Almus environs), *D. s. parabouilloni* **ssp. n.** (Giresun province, type locality: Bulancak environs), *D. s. tatari* **ssp. n.** (Erzurum province, Kireçli Pass environs). *D. carolisturani* Breuning & Ruspoli, 1971 and *D. bouilloni* Breuning & Ruspoli, 1975 are downgraded to subspecies rank as *Dorcadion scrobicolle carolisturani* Breuning & Ruspoli, 1971, **stat. n.** and *Dorcadion scrobicolle bouilloni* Breuning & Ruspoli, 1975, **stat. n.** New synonyms are proposed: *D. (C.) kizildagense* Bernhauer & Peks, 2012 = *D. (C.) karacaorense* Bernhauer & Peks, 2012, **syn. n.** Type locality of *D. scrobicolle* is accepted as mountain areas of Çorum and Yozgat - according to the traditional interpretation of the taxon.

Key words

Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, Dorcadionini, *Dorcadion*, taxonomy, new subspecies, new synonyms, Turkey.

Introduction

Cerambycidae fauna of Turkey rests poorly investigated up to now. We see many taxonomy problems in a very interesting genus *Dorcadion*, which is distributed all over the country and represented in Turkey by more than 500 species. Many taxa regarded as species up to now are in fact closely related subspecies. We see such a situation around *D. scrobicolle* Kraatz, 1873. Unfortunately, this species was described without exact type locality.

Taxonomical part

Family Cerambycidae Latreille, 1802

Subfamily Lamiinae Latreille, 1825

Tribe Dorcadionini Swainson, 1840

Genus *Dorcadion* Dalman, 1817

Type species:

Cerambyx glycyrrhizae Pallas, 1773

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) scrobicolle Kraatz, 1873

Figs 1-21

Dorcadion scrobicolle Kraatz, 1873: 97 - "Klein-Asien"; Ganglbauer, 1884: 497 - "Kleinasien"; Fuchs & Breuning, 1971: 437 - "Yozgat", "Yaylacik-Orman (Tokat)"; Braun, 1978: 110 - "Yozgat prov., 5 km N

Material and methods

Specimens were photographed under a microscope AmScope SM745NTP with an attached Canon PowerShot G10 digital camera equipped with Cannon Zoom lens 5X IS 6.1-30.5 mm 1:2.8-4.5. The illustrations were edited with Adobe Photoshop 7.0 and Helicon Focus 3.20.

Yozgat, 1400 m"; Adlbauer, 1992: 501 - "Topçam Mountain., Tokat, 1400 m", "Gökdere, Yakacık NE Tokat, 900 m"; Özdikmen, 2012b: 1134.

Dorcadion (s. str.) *scrobicolle*, Winkler, 1929: 1192 - "Asia Minor".

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) scrobicolle, Breuning, 1962: 371 - "Amasya, Tokat".

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) scrobicolle m. *fuscobrevestitum* Breuning, 1962: 372 - Tokat prov.: "Niksar" (female).

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) cinerarium heinzi Breuning, 1964: 1 - "Egribel-Pass, 2600-2400m".

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) carolisturani Breuning & Ruspoli, 1971: 128 - "Anatoliae".

Dorcadion scrobicolle fuscobrevestitum Fuchs & Breuning, 1971: 437 - "Yaylacik-Orman (Tokat)".

- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) bouilloni* Breuning & Ruspoli, 1975: 116 - "Mesodye, entre Samsun et Koyulhisar (Anatolie)".
- Dorcadion heinzi*, Braun, 1978: 109, part. - "Eğribel-Pass, 2400-2600m"; 1979: 81, part. - "Eğribel-Pass".
- Dorcadion carolisturani*, Braun, 1978: 110, part. - "Anat. bor. Paß zw. Gököy u. Mesudivo 1800 m"; 1979: 82, part. - "Pass von Kümbet" - (?= *D. heinzi* Breuning); Sama, 1982: 223, part. - "Ordu: passo tra Mesudiye e Gököy, 1400 m"; Özdikmen, 2012b: 1131, part.
- Dorcadion scrobicolle morulum* Holzschuh, 1995: 42 - "Anatolia bor., NE Tokat, Gökdere; Tokat Pass zwischen Tokat und Niksar".
- Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) carolisturani*, Özdikmen, 2007: 296, part. - Ordu prov., Giresun prov.; 2010: 420, part. - Bayburt prov., Giresun prov., Ordu prov.; 2012a: 762, part.; 2016: 2410, part.; Danilevsky, 2010: 244, part.; 2020: 342, part.
- Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) heinzi*, Özdikmen, 2007: 300, part. - Giresun prov.; 2010: 435, part. - Giresun prov.; 2012a: 766, part.; 2016: 2421, part.; Danilevsky, 2010: 247, part.; 2020: 347, part.
- Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) scrobicolle*, Özdikmen, 2007: 309 - Amasya prov., Tokat prov., Yozgat prov.; 2010: 468 - Amasya prov., Tokat prov., Yozgat prov.; 2012a: 775; 2016: 2442.
- Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) bouilloni*, Danilevsky, 2010: 244, part.; 2020: 342, part.; Özdikmen, 2012a: 762, part.; 2016: 2409, part.
- Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) scrobicolle scrobicolle*, Danilevsky, 2010: 252, part.; 2020: 356, part.
- Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) scrobicolle morulum*, Danilevsky, 2010: 252, part.; 2020: 356, part.
- Dorcadion bouilloni*, Özdikmen, 2012b: 1130, part.

Type locality

Mountains of Çorum and Yozgat - according to the traditional interpretation of the taxon.

Description

Body of moderate size, regularly oval.

Head usually glabrous, only females could have poor head pubescence in certain populations; frons with sparse irregular punctation; vertex with rough rugose sculpture and several big dots.

Antennae thick, reaching elytral middle in females or surpassing 2nd elytral third in males; 1st antennal joint usually red, dark-red, or black, covered by dirty-white pubescence; other joints nearly always black, or sometimes partly dark-red; genae a little narrower than lower eye lobes; 3rd joint shorter than scapus, but longer than 4th; pedicellum very short, strongly transverse.

Prothorax in females about 1.2 times shorter than basal width; in males from as long as basal width to 1.2 times shorter than basal width; with distinct lateral tubercles in males, which are slightly obliterated in

females; pronotum roughly sculptured, with more or less dense, big or small, irregular punctation, glabrous or sometimes in females with reduced pubescence, without white central setae line, without or with hardly pronounced central longitudinal depression; scutellum small, triangular, with very fine pale pubescence.

Elytra smooth, glabrous, strongly shining or sometimes in females (and very rarer in males) with very poor reduced pubescence, widest near middle, with indistinct fine sparse punctation, more evident in females; humeral carinae poorly developed anteriorly; no other carinae present; only sutural and marginal (along epipleurae) white stripes present; humeral elytral stripe sometimes visible; subsutural velvety black line absent.

Legs with moderately dense pale fine pubescence; 1st tarsal joint of hind legs about as long as 2nd and 3rd combined; lobes of 3rd joint rounded; emargination of 3rd joint relatively small, not reaching its middle.

Ventral body side with very fine, dense, pale pubescence; last abdominal sternite shallowly emarginated, pygidium and postpygidium in males widely rounded; last abdominal tergite in females truncated.

Body totally black, antennae and legs can be partly red.

Females are similar to males, but body much wider; usually androchromal, but sometimes can be autochromal with poor elytral pubescence.

Body length (to elytral apices) in males: 9.5-15.2 mm, in females: 11.8-18.2 mm; body width (at elytral middle) in males: 3.7-6.0 mm, in females: 4.5-7.1 mm.

Differential diagnosis

Prothorax with very short lateral spines; pronotum in males glabrous with very rough sculpture; males with shining elytra, females sometimes with poorly pubescent elytra; elytral punctation indistinct, sutural and marginal elytral white stripes present in males; humeral and dorsal stripes usually absent; subsutural black stripes absent.

Distribution

9 provinces in the North of Central and East Anatolia: Çorum, Yozgat, Amasya, Tokat, Ordu, Giresun, Sivas, Bayburt, Erzurum.

1. *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) scrobicolle scrobicolle* Kraatz, 1873

Figs 1-5, 21 (1-3)

Dorcadion scrobicolle Kraatz, 1873: 97 - "Klein-Asien"; Fuchs & Breuning, 1971: 437, part. - "Yozgat", "Yaylacik-Orman (Tokat)"; Braun, 1978: 110 - "Yozgat prov., 5 km N Yozgat, 1400 m".

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) scrobicolle, Breuning, 1962: 371 - "Amasya, Tokat".

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) scrobicolle, Özdikmen,

2007: 309 - Amasya prov., Tokat prov., Yozgat prov.;
2010: 468 - Amasya prov., Tokat prov., Yozgat prov.;
2012a: 775; 2016: 2442.

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) scrobicolle scrobicolle,
Danilevsky, 2010: 252, part.; 2020: 356, part.

Type locality

Mountains of Çorum and Yozgat - according to the traditional interpretation of the taxon.

Diagnosis

Body black, antennae and legs black; elytra very smooth, glabrous in males and usually in females, but sometimes female elytra with very fine reduced brownish pubescence; humeral and dorsal stripes always absent; body length in males: 11-14.8 mm, in females: 14.0-18.2 mm; body width in males: 4.5-6.0 mm, in females: 6.4-7.1 mm.

Materials

2 males, Çorum, İskilip, IV.1977, W. Heinz - collection of M. Danilevsky; 3 males, 5 females, Yozgat, Sorgun, Eymir environs, 1700 m, 14.5.2000, D. Obydov - collection of M. Danilevsky.

Distribution.

Turkey, Çorum province, İskilip (40°44'N, 34°28'E); Turkey, Yozgat province: Sorgun, Eymir environs (40°4'26"N, 35°13'14"E), 1700 m and 5 km N Yozgat, 1400 m. The records from Amasya and Tokat by Breuning, 1962 could also be connected with nominative subspecies.

2. *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) scrobicolle morulum* Holzschuh, 1995

Fig. 6, 21 (4-9)

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) scrobicolle m. *fuscobrevestitum* Breuning, 1962: 372 - Tokat prov.: "Niksar" (female).

Dorcadion scrobicolle fuscobrevestitum Fuchs & Breuning, 1971: 437, part. - "Yozgat", "Yaylacik-Orman (Tokat)" [unavailable name].

Dorcadion scrobicolle, Adlbauer, 1992: 501 - "Topçam Mountain., Tokat, 1400 m", "Gökdere, Yakacık NE Tokat, 900 m".

Dorcadion scrobicolle morulum Holzschuh, 1995: 42 - "Anatolia bor., NE Tokat, Gökdere; Tokat Pass zwischen Tokat und Niksar"; Özdikmen, 2012b: 1134.

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) scrobicolle morulum, Danilevsky, 2010: 252, part.; 2020: 356, part.; Özdikmen, 2012a: 775; 2016: 2442 - Tokat province.

Type locality

Turkey, north-east of Tokat province, Gökdere [40°28'12"N, 36°45'13"E], 750 m.

Diagnosis

According to the original description, body black with reddish legs and antennae; males with fine rudimental elytral pubescence; humeral elytral stripe sometimes visible; females with dark-brown elytral pubescence; size: 10,5-14,6 mm.

Remark

Dorcadion scrobicolle m. *fuscobrevestitum* Breuning, 1962: 372 was described from Tokat province, "Niksar" [40°35'34"N, 36°57'11"E] on the base of a series of females. That locality is very close to "Gökdere, Tokat Pass zwischen Tokat und Niksar", where *D. s. morulum* Holzschuh, 1995 was described from. The publication of *D. s. fuscobrevestitum* by Fuchs & Breuning (1971) did not make the name available, as two names were recorded by authors for one locality (Yaylacik-Orman): *D. scrobicolle* and *D. s. fuscobrevestitum* Br., so the authors "expressly gave it infrasubspecific rank" (Art. 45.6.4.).

Distribution

Turkey, six localities in Tokat province: Gökdere [40°28'12"N, 36°45'13"E] environs, 750 m; Yakacık [40°28'48"N, 36°42'22"E], 900 m; Tokat Pass [40°31'34"N, 36°50'29"E] between Tokat and Niksar; Yaylacık, 40°43'43"N, 36°40'37"E; Niksar [40°35'34"N, 36°57'11"E] environs; Topçam Mountain. [40°24'37"N, 36°33'27"E], 1400 m.

3. *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) scrobicolle hroni* ssp. n.

Figs 7-10, 21 (10)

Type locality

Turkey, south-east of Tokat province, Almus [40°22'29.28"N, 36°54'11.09"E] environs.

Diagnosis

Pronotum similar to *D. s. morulum* with less rough punctation. But legs of all specimens are totally black (as in *D. s. bouilloni*) and elytra in all males are totally glabrous and strongly shining; females are partly autochromal; one female with poorly developed brown elytral pubescence and one female with dense elytral pubescence; both females with sutural and humeral elytral stripes; body length in males: 12.2-15.2 mm, body width: 4.7-5.3 mm, body length in females: 14.0-16.9 mm, width: 6.0-6.5 mm.

Material

Holotype, male, Turkey, Tokat province, Almus environs, 1.6.1992, J. Hron leg. - collection of M. Lazarev (Moscow); 32 paratypes (18 males and 14 females) - collection of J. Hron (Rokycany, Czech Republic) & S. Murzin (Moscow); 17 males, 14 females with same label; 1 male from same locality with same date, but Z. Hanousek leg.

Distribution

Turkey, south-east of Tokat province, Almus [40°22'29.28"N, 36°54'11.09"E] environs.

Etymology

The new subspecies is dedicated to Jan Hron, who collected the type series.

4. *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) scrobicollae bouilloni* Breuning & Ruspoli, 1975, stat. n.

Figs 11-12, 21 (11-12)

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) bouilloni Breuning & Ruspoli, 1975: 116 - "Mesodye, entre Samsun et Koyulhisar (Anatolie)".

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) bouilloni, Danilevsky, 2010: 244; 2020: 342; Özdikmen, 2012a: 762; 2016: 2409.

Dorcadion bouilloni, Özdikmen, 2012b: 1130.

Type locality

"Mesodye [40°27'50"N, 37°46'21"E] environs, entre Samsun et Koyulhisar (Anatolie)".

Diagnosis

Pronotum with very rough, conjugated punctation; 1st antennal joint and legs totally black; male elytra smooth, strongly shining; elytra in females with very fine rudimental pubescence; body length of available males: 10.5-12.0 mm, width: 4.1-5.0 mm; body length of available female: 11.8 mm, width: 4.6 mm; according to the original description, the length of holotype-female 13 mm, width: 4.5-5 mm.

Material

3 males & 1 female, Turkey, Ordu prov., Mesudiye, 27.5.2000 V. Skoupý leg. - collection of M. Danilevsky (Moscow); 1 male, Turkey, N Sivas, Koyulhisar, 1.6.1992, J. Hron leg. - collection of S. Murzin (Moscow).

Distribution

Turkey, southernmost area of Ordu province, Mesudiye [40°27'50"N, 37°46'21"E] environs and northern part of Sivas province Koyulhisar [40°18'19"N, 37°49'50"E] environs.

5. *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) scrobicollae parabouilloni* ssp. n.

Figs 13-14, 21 (13-15)

Type locality

Turkey, Giresun province, Bulancak, Bektaş Plateau, 40°39'03.67"N, 38°14'24.98"E, 2053 m.

Description

Body in males about 2.4-2.7 times longer than

maximal elytral width, in females about 2.4 times (body length from mandibles to elytral apex); head glabrous; frons shining, with sparse irregular punctation; vertex with rough rugose sculpture and several big dots; 1st antennal joint usually red, dark-red, or rarely black, densely covered by dirty-white pubescence; other joints nearly always black, or sometimes partly dark-red; genae a little narrower than lower eye lobes; prothorax in females about 1.2 times shorter than basal width; in males from as long as basal width to 1.2 times shorter than basal width; with distinct lateral tubercles in males, which are slightly obliterated in females; pronotum roughly sculptured, with more or less dense, small, irregular punctation, glabrous, without white central setae line, without or with hardly pronounced central longitudinal depression; females androchromal, with glabrous shining elytra; body totally black, including antennae with the exception of dark-red scapus; legs also dark-red with black tarsi; body length (to elytral apices) in males: 9.5-10.8 mm, in females: 12.6-13.3 mm; body width (at elytral middle) in males: 3.7-4.4 mm, in females: 5.2-5.8 mm.

Differential diagnosis

The new subspecies is very close to *D. s. bouilloni* Breuning & Ruspoli, 1975 because of about same size, similarly punctured, glabrous pronotum without white central line and glabrous strongly shining elytra. But in *D. s. bouilloni* pronotal punctation usually denser, with often conjugated punctures; pronotal tubercles more acute; antennae and legs totally black; female with distinct elytral pubescence.

Material

Holotype, male, Turkey, Giresun, Bulancak, Bektaş Plateau, 40°39'03.67"N, 38°14'24.98"E, 2053 m, 27.6.2017, leg. M. Tatar - collection of M. Lazarev (Moscow); 24 paratypes (20 males, 4 females) - collections of M. Lazarev and Entomology Museum Erzurum, Turkey (EMET); 3 males and 2 females with same label as in holotype; 11 males and 1 female from same locality, but collected on 5.7.2019 by M. Tatar; 5 males, Turkey, Giresun, Bulancak, Yaslibahçe Village, 40°51'27.94"N, 38°12'53"E, 503 m, 11.7.2019, leg. M. Tatar; 1 male, 1 female, Turkey, Giresun, Bulancak, Pazarsuyu environs, 40°55'39.43"N, 38°10'43.39"E, 50 m, 15.7.2019, leg. M. Tatar.

Distribution.

Turkey, Giresun province: Bulancak, Bektaş Plateau, 40°39'03.67"N, 38°14'24.98"E, 2053 m; Yaslibahçe Village, 40°51'27.94"N, 38°12'53"E, 503 m; Pazarsuyu environs, 40°55'39.43"N, 38°10'43.39"E, 50 m.

6. *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) scrobicolle carolisturani* Breuning & Ruspoli, 1971, stat. n.

Figs 15-16, 21 (16-17)

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) carolisturani Breuning & Ruspoli, 1971: 128 - "Anatoliae".

Dorcadion carolisturani, Braun, 1978: 110, part. - "Anat. bor. Pass zw. Gököy u. Mesudiye 1800 m"; 1979: 82 - "Pass von Kümbet" - (?= *D. heinzi* Breuning); Özdikmen, 2012b: 1131.

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) carolisturani, Özdikmen, 2007: 296 - Ordu prov., Giresun prov.; 2010: 420, part. - Bayburt prov., Giresun prov., Ordu prov.; 2012a: 762; 2016: 2410; Danilevsky, 2010: 244; 2020: 342.

Type locality

According to Tavakilian & Chevillotte (2020): "Turquie, Chaîne Pontique (Giresun) Col de Kümbet entre Giresun et Şebinkarahisar" - on the base of holotype label.

Diagnosis

Pronotum with moderately rough punctation; 1st antennal joint and legs red; elytra in males and females glabrous, shining; length of available male: 11.5 mm, length of available female: 13 mm; according to the original description the size of specimens 10-13 mm.

Material

Male, Turkey, Giresun, S Kümbet, 2100 m, 2.6.1991, K. Slaven leg. - collection of V. Skoupý; female, Giresun, Tamdere, 30.5.1992, V. Skoupý leg. - collection of V. Skoupý.

Distribution

Turkey, Central part of Giresun province: southwards Kümbet Pass [40°33'N, 38°26'E] 2100 m and Tamdere [40°31'N, 38°22'E] environs.

Remarks

The record of "*Dorcadion carolisturani*" by Braun (1978: 110) from Ordu, "Pass zw. Gököy u. Mesudiye, 1800 m" was most probably connected with the local population of *D. s. bouilloni*.

A publication of *D. carolisturani* m. *bayburtense* Breuning, 1975 from near Bayburt [40°15'35"N, 40°13'40"E] (Fig. 21: 22) can not be connected with *D. carolisturani* because of too big distance of the local population from its area.

7. *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) scrobicolle heinzi* Breuning, 1964

Fig. 17, 21 (18)

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) cinerarium heinzi Breuning, 1964: 1 - "Egribel-Pass, 2600-2400 m".

Dorcadion heinzi, Braun, 1978: 109 - "Egribel-Pass, 2400-2600m"; 1979: 81 - "Egribel-Pass".

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) heinzi, Özdikmen, 2007: 300 - Giresun prov.; 2010: 435 - Giresun prov.; 2012a: 766; 2016: 2421; Danilevsky, 2010: 247; 2020: 347.

Type locality

Turkey, Giresun province, Egribel-Pass [40°27'23"N, 38°23'51"E, 2235 m], 2400-2600 m.

Diagnosis

Pronotum with moderately rough punctation; 1st antennal joint and legs red; elytra in females with very fine rudimental pubescence; length of available female: 15.5 mm, width: 6.1 mm.

Material

Female, Turkey, Giresun prov., Egribel Pass, 06.06.2003, P. Bialooki leg. - collection of M. Danilevsky (Moscow)

Distribution

Turkey, Giresun province, Egribel Pass [40°27'23"N, 38°23'51"E, 2235 m], 2400-2600 m.

8. *Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) scrobicolle tatar* ssp. n.

Figs 18-20, 21 (19-21)

Type locality

Turkey, Erzurum province, Kireçli Pass [40°19'13.02"N, 41°42'52.98"E], 2415 m.

Diagnosis

The specie is very similar to *D. s. parabouilloni* ssp. n. Body black with red 1st antennal joint, femora and tibiae; other antennal joint dark red, often nearly black as well as tarsi; thorax glabrous with very rough partly contiguous punctation; lateral thoracic spines very, often obliterated; elytra glabrous, strongly shining with indistinct punctation, with white sutural and marginal stripes; dorsal and humeral stripes totally absent; subsutural velvety black stripes also totally absent; body length in males: 9.8-11.5 mm, width: 3.8-4.2 mm; body length in females: 13.0-15.0 mm, width: 5.0-5.5 mm.

Differential diagnosis

The new subspecies easily differs from *D. s. parabouilloni* ssp. n. by distinctly denser conjugating pronotal punctation. Besides *D. s. tatar* ssp. n. strongly distant from *D. s. parabouilloni* ssp. n. geographically.

Material

Holotype, male, Turkey, Erzurum - Narman, Kireçli Pass, 2415 m, 25.5.2019, M. Tatar leg. - collection of M. Lazarev (Moscow); 6 paratypes (4 males and 2 females)

- collection of M. Lazarev (Moscow) and collection of Entomology Museum Erzurum, Turkey (EMET); 2 males with same label; 1 male from same locality but collected on 15.6.2019, M. Tatar leg.; 1 male, Erzurum - Narman, Sülüklü Village, 2145m, 25.5.2019, M. Tatar leg.; 2 females, Turkey, Erzurum - Horasan, Bulgurlu Village, 28.5.2019, M. Tatar leg.

Distribution

Turkey, North east part of Erzurum province; 3 localities known: Kireçli Pass [40°19'13.02"N, 41°42'52.98"E], 2415 m; Sülüklü Village [40°18'46.14"N, 41°49'14.39"E], 2145 m; Bulgurlu Village [40°11'15"N, 42°15'41"E], 1870 m.

Etymology

The new taxon is dedicated to our young co-author and friend Muhammed Tatar, who collected the type series.

Remark

D. (C.) kizildagense Bernhauer & Peks, 2012 and *D. (C.) karacaorenense* Bernhauer & Peks, 2012 were described from very close localities (Kızıladağ eastwards Imranlı, 1800m [about 39°52'13"N, 38°6'34"E] and 9 km south-eastwards Imranlı, 1800 m [about 39°50'10"N, 38°10'36"E]). More over both were recorded from one locality Corakboğazi [pass 39°46'19"N, 38°10'58"E], n. Karaçaören 1800 m According to the original descriptions the morphological differences between two taxa are very small.

The differential characters listed by the authors could not be applied to both species, so *D. (C.) kizildagense* Bernhauer & Peks, 2012 = *D. (C.) karacaorenense* Bernhauer & Peks, 2012, **syn. n.**

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) kizildagense Bernhauer & Peks, 2012

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) kizildagense Bernhauer & Peks, 2012: 212 - "Kızıladağ, ö. Imranlı [about 39°52'13"N, 38° 6'34"E], ö Sivas, 1800 m"; "Kızıladağ, ö. Imranlı, ö Sivas, 2000 m"; "Corakboğazi [pass 39°46'19"N, 38°10'58"E], n. Karaçaören 1800 m"; "s. Boğazören, n. Karaçaören, ö. Imranlı, 1800 m" [same locality]; "w. Refahiye: Gemecik [39°53'22"N, 38°26'33"E]"; "Kızıladağ Pass [39°51'36"N, 38°25'40"E], 1950 m".

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) kizildagense, Bernhauer & Peks, 2014: 336; Danilevsky, 2020: 348, part.

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) karacaorenense Bernhauer & Peks, 2012: 211, **syn. n.** - "9 km sö. Imranlı, ö. Sivas, 1800 m"; "15 km sö. Imranlı, ö. Sivas, 1800 m"; "n. Bogazören, n. Karaçaören, ö. Sivas, 1800 m" [about 39°49'26"N, 38°10'54"E]; "sw. Refahiye [39°54'N, 38°46'E], w. Erzinçan,

1700 m"; "Çorakboğazi, n. Karaçaören, ö. Sivas".

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) karacaorenense, Bernhauer & Peks, 2014: 336.

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) karacaorenense, Lazarev, 2014: 279; Danilevsky, 2020: 348, part.

Type locality.

Turkey, East Sivas province, Kızıladağ eastwards Imranlı [39°52'13"N, 38°6'34"E], 1800 m.

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Figures 1-5. *D. (C.) s. scrobicolle* Kraatz, 1873: 1- male, Sorgun env., Eymir, 1700 m, 14.5.2000, D. Obydov leg.; 2- androchromal female with same label; 3- autochromal female with same label; 4- male, Çorum, İskilip, IV.1977, W. Heinz leg. 5- female with same label; **Figure 6.** *D. (C.) s. morulum* Holzschuh, 1995, male, photo from Holzschuh (1995);

Figures 7-10. *D. (C.) s. hroni* ssp. n.: 7- holotype, male; 8- paratype, male; 9- paratype, androchromal female; 10- paratype, autochromal female (photo by J. Hron); **Figures 11-12.** *D. (C.) s. bouilloni* Breuning & Ruspoli, 1975, stat. n.: 11- male, Ordu prov., Mesudiye, 27.5.2000 V. Skopý leg.; 12- female with same label; **Figures 13-14.** *D. (C.) s. parabouilloni* ssp. n.: 13- holotype, male; 14- paratype, female;

Figures 15-16. *D. (C.) s. carolisturani* Breuning & Ruspoli, 1971, **stat. n.**: 15- male, Giresun, S Kümbet, 2100 m, 2.6.1991, K. Slaven leg.; 16- female, Giresun, Tamdere, 30.5.1992, V. Skoupý leg.; **Figure 17.** *D. (C.) s. heinzi* Breuning, 1964 - female, Giresun province, Egribel-Pass, 2400-2600 m, W. Heinz leg.; **Figures 18-20.** *D. (C.) s. tatari* **ssp. n.**: 18- holotype, male; 19- paratype, male, Erzurum, Narman Sülüklü 25.5.2019 M. Tatar leg.; 20 - paratype, female, Erzurum, Horasan, Bulgurlu, 28.5.2019, M. Tatar leg.

Figure 21. Map of the area of *D. (C.) scrobicolle* Kraatz, 1873 in Turkey

D. (C.) s. scrobicolle Kraatz, 1873: **1**- Yozgat province, Sorgun, Eymir environs (40°4'26"N, 35°13'14"E), 1700 m; **2**- Yozgat province, 5 km N Yozgat, 1400 m; **3**- Çorum province, İskilip (40°44'N, 34°28'E); *D. (C.) s. morulum* Holzschuh, 1995: Tokat province: **4**- Gökdere [40°28'12"N, 36°45'13"E] environs, 750 m; **5**- Yakacık [40°28'48"N, 36°42'22"E], 900 m; **6**- Topçam Mountain. [40°24'37"N, 36°33'27"E], 1400 m; **7**- Tokat Pass [40°31'34"N, 36°50'29"E] between Tokat and Niksar **8**- Niksar [40°35'34"N, 36°57'11"E] environs; **9**- Yaylacık, 40°43'43"N, 36°40'37"E. *D. (C.) s. hroni* ssp. n.: **10**- Tokat province, Almus [40°22'29.28"N, 36°54'11.09"E] environs. *D. (C.) s. bouilloni* Breuning & Ruspoli, 1975, stat. n.: **11**- Ordu province, Mesudiye [40°27'50"N, 37°46'21"E] environs; **12**- Sivas province Koyulhisar [40°18'19"N, 37°49'50"E] environs. *D. (C.) s. parabouilloni* ssp. n.: Giresun province: **13**- Bulancak, Bektas Plateau, 40°39'03.67"N, 38°14'24.98"E, 2053 m; **14**- Yaslıbahçe Village, 40°51'27.94"N, 38°12'53"E, 503 m; **15**- Pazarsuyu environs, 40°55'39.43"N, 38°10' 43.39"E, 50 m. *D. (C.) s. carolisturani* Breuning & Ruspoli, 1971, stat. n. : Giresun province: **16**- southwards Kümbet Pass [40°33'N, 38°26'E] 2100 m; **17**- Tamdere [40°31'N, 38°22'E] environs. *D. (C.) s. heinzi* Breuning, 1964: **18**- Giresun province, Egribel-Pass [40°27'23"N, 38°23'51"E, 2235 m], 2400-2600 m. *D. (C.) s. tatar* ssp. n.: Erzurum province: 3 localities known: **19**- Kireçli Pass [40°19'13.02"N, 41°42'52.98"E], 2415 m; **20**- Sülüklü Village [40°18'46.14"N, 41°49'14.39"E], 2145 m; **21**- Bulgurlu Village [40°11'15"N, 42°15'41"E], 1870 m. *D. (C.) scrobicolle* ssp.: **22**- Bayburt province, Bayburt [40°15'35"N, 40°13'40"E].